

Extraction Methodology of the Substrate Parasitic Network of an RF-MOSFET with Separate Substrate DC Connection

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Abstract—In this paper, a methodology to extract the parasitic substrate network of an RF-MOSFET with a channel length of 80 nm and a width of 3 μm is proposed. In this transistor, the source is disconnected from the active area, which is the substrate connection. The device presents a separate substrate DC connection, which allows varying the bulk potential. A mathematical formulation to find the source junction capacitance in the high-frequency regime, as a function of bulk potential, is presented for the first time. This capacitance influences the behavior of the output port of the device at high frequencies. In fact, excellent agreement between measurement and model was obtained up to 20 GHz. In addition, this proposal was used to characterize RF-MOSFET devices using two-port S-parameter measurements without having the source and substrate connected. This was possible because all capacitances were determined independently, which allowed us to determine an accurate electrical model, which makes it possible to simulate the performance of the device when varying the substrate potential in the RF regime.

Index terms— RF MOSFET, parameter extraction, substrate parasitic network.

I. INTRODUCTION

RF-MOSFETs have been increasingly used for high frequency applications, and thus the need for accurate models to describe the MOSFET in this regime is evident. In these, the substrate parasitic network is a critical element in their characterization and modeling. Furthermore, it is not always possible to connect the source to substrate in most applications. For example, the substrate terminal of one of the two transistors in a cascode amplifier is not shorted to the source [1]. Also, the substrate resistance dramatically influences the operation of the circuit in both common-gate and common-drain topology. Therefore, it is essential to fully characterize this type of transistor. Therefore, an extraction methodology that considers the separate substrate terminal is required.

Several recent articles have focused on the extraction of the substrate parasitic network [2-3]. In reference [2], all parameters are extracted from three-port S-parameter

measurement data, but gate resistance is ignored. The circuit used in this case is extremely simplified based on certain considerations [3]. Initially, the equivalent circuit assumes that the source and drain junction capacitances are equal. This is also assumed for the gate-to-source and gate-to-drain capacitances. Furthermore, the effect of the substrate is represented by a single resistor. Also, source and drain are shorted. On the other hand, the substrate parasitic network in [4] and [5] is based on the series connection of a resistor and a capacitor, which means that the junction capacitance between source and substrate is neglected. In this paper, a method to directly extract substrate resistance and capacitances is proposed. Unlike [3], the capacitances are independently found, and the gate resistance is taken into account. The model was verified using an RF-MOSFET with a separate substrate DC connection, obtaining a very good correlation.

II. EXPERIMENT

Fig. 1. Layout of the device under test (DUT) consisting of an RF-MOSFET surrounded by the pads in ground-signal-ground (GSG) configuration.

A Vector Network Analyzer (VNA) and ground-signal-ground coplanar Cascade probes of 100 μm pitch were

employed to measure the on-wafer two-port S-parameters, as shown in Fig. 1. The applied power was 10 μ W. Before device measurements, the system was calibrated using the LRM procedure (Line - Reflect - Match). The device under test (DUT) was an RF-NMOS with $L_m = 80$ nm, $W_f = 3$ μ m and $NF = 64$. Additionally, this transistor has a substrate terminal, which is disconnected from the source. It allows for a DC bias to be applied to the substrate while performing the RF measurements. The device was turned off to allow us to determine the substrate parasitic network.

Before interpreting the measured data, the pad parasitic effects were removed using the de-embedding technique outlines in [6] and [7], for which two additional dummy structures were measured. These were an open and a short-all.

Fig. 2. Equivalent circuit of an RF-MOSFET when it is turned off and the intrinsic parameters are neglected. In a) all substrate parameters are considered and b) R_{dsb1} and R_{dsb2} resistances are very small and not taken into account in the scheme, where R_b is $R_{sb} \parallel R_{db}$.

The equivalent circuit without neglecting the substrate parasitic parameters is shown in Fig. 2(a), without considering the intrinsic parameters. C_{js} and C_{jd} are the source and drain junction capacitances; C_{gs} , C_{gd} and C_{gb} represent the gate-to-source, gate-to-drain and gate-to-substrate capacitances, respectively; R_{sb} , R_{db} , R_{dsb1} and R_{dsb2} correspond to resistances from source and drain to substrate. Since R_{dsb1} and R_{dsb2} are very small, the circuit can be simplified to that shown in Fig. 2(b). Furthermore, as is shown [2] R_{dsb1} and R_{dsb2} are about 2.5% of R_{sb} and R_{db} , and thus, R_{sb} and R_{db} can be placed in parallel, which is indicated as R_b in the figure.

III. PROPOSED METHOD AND RESULTS

Fig. 3 illustrates the linear regression of experimental data in order to find the elements of the substrate parasitic network. Initially, the C_{gd} , C_{jd} , C_{gs} , and C_{gb} capacitances are obtained using (1) through (4), and then resistances R_g y R_b are determined with (5) and (6).

$$-\text{Im}(Y_{12}) \approx \omega C_{gd} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Im}(Y_{22}) \approx \omega(C_{gd} + C_{jd}) \quad (2)$$

$$-\frac{1}{\text{Im}(Z_{22})} \approx \omega \left(C_{jd} + \frac{C_{gs}C_{gd}}{C_{gs} + C_{gd}} \right) \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Im}(Y_{11}) \approx \omega(C_{gs} + C_{gd} + C_{gb}) \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Re}(Y_{11}) \approx \omega^2 R_g (C_{gs} + C_{gd} + C_{gb})^2 \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Re}(Y_{22}) \approx \omega^2 R_b C_{jd}^2 \quad (6)$$

The Y_{22} admittance and Z_{22} impedance were adjusted up to 4 GHz, since at these frequencies the effect of the C_{js} junction capacitance is not appreciable. This is due to the parallel combination of C_{js} and R_b in the RF-MOSFET equivalent circuit, in the off bias condition. In Fig. 3 the capacitive behavior of Y_{22} can be observed, as well as in the inverse of Z_{22} . On the other hand, C_{js} was determined at frequencies above 6 GHz from Y' . The admittance Y' represents the reduction of the equivalent circuit of Y_{22} (see Fig. 4(a)) by subtracting all elements up to C_{js} . For this reason, a delta-star transformation of impedances was performed at nodes 1 to 3, as shown in Fig. 4(b). At this point, it is important to remark that the source and substrate terminals are connected to the same AC node because the DC bias between the source and substrate is applied through a compensated CASCADE DC probe. Thus, the components were then determined using (7) through (11). As can be observed, the experimental data and the simulation results were in agreement up to 20 GHz.

$$Z_1 = \frac{1}{j\omega C_{gd} C_{gb} \left(\frac{1}{C_{gd}} + \frac{1}{C_{jd}} + \frac{1}{C_{gb}} \right)} \quad (7)$$

$$Z_2 = \frac{1}{j\omega C_{gd} C_{jd} \left(\frac{1}{C_{gd}} + \frac{1}{C_{jd}} + \frac{1}{C_{gb}} \right)} \quad (8)$$

$$Z_3 = \frac{1}{j\omega C_{gb} C_{jd} \left(\frac{1}{C_{gd}} + \frac{1}{C_{jd}} + \frac{1}{C_{gb}} \right)} \quad (9)$$

$$Z_4 = R_g \parallel \frac{1}{j\omega C_{gs}} \quad (10)$$

$$\text{Im} \frac{1}{\frac{1}{\frac{1}{Y_{22}} + Z_2} - \frac{1}{Z_1 + Z_4}} - Z_3} = \text{Im}(Y') = \omega C_{js} \quad (11)$$

Fig. 3. Linear regression of experimental data for the parameter extraction of an RF-NMOS device, with $L_m=80\text{nm}$, $W_f=3\mu\text{m}$ and $NF=64$. Also, V_{gs} , V_{ds} , V_{bs} are equal to 0V.

Fig. 4. The equivalent circuit for Y_{22} . The nodes are drain (D), source (S) and substrate (B). Also, V_{gs} , V_{ds} , V_{bs} are equal to 0V.

TABLE I. EXTRACTED PARAMETER VALUES

Parameter	Extracted value	Unit
C_{gd}	60.2	fF
C_{jd}	102.5	fF
C_{gs}	62.2	fF
C_{gb}	3.0	fF
R_g	2.8	Ω
R_b	50.1	Ω
C_{js}	98.2	fF

Table I lists, in order of extraction, the parameters obtained from linear regressions of the experimental data. It is clear that C_{js} y C_{jd} are of the same order of magnitude, which is also true for C_{gs} y C_{gb} . On the other hand, C_{gb} is only 5% of C_{gs} y C_{gb} .

Figures 5 through 7 show the comparison of S-parameters between experimental data and simulations of the proposed model (with C_{js} and C_{gb}) and of the model in [3] and [4] (without C_{js} and C_{gb}). Here, it is assumed that S_{12} is equal to S_{21} . In addition, significant differences are observed in S_{22} above 6 GHz. This allows neglecting the C_{js} capacitance in the low-frequency range. Therefore, this capacitance can be obtained at higher frequencies.

Fig. 5. Experimental and simulated data with/without C_{js} and C_{gb} for the magnitude and phase of S_{11} . Also, V_{gs} , V_{ds} , V_{bs} are equal to 0V.

Fig. 6. Experimental and simulated data with/without C_{js} and C_{gb} for the magnitude and phase of S_{12} . Also, V_{gs} , V_{ds} , V_{bs} are equal to 0V.

Figure 8 compares the proposed model to the one presented in [2] for S_{22} . The considerations in [2], $C_{gs}=C_{gb}$ and $C_{js}=C_{jd}$, do not allow for a precise adjustment of S_{22} at high frequencies, whereas the proposed model does. In addition, R_g is not taken into account. In fact, R_g does not affect the extraction of most of the parameters of the substrate parasitic network except for C_{js} , as shown in equations (10) and (11). If R_g is neglected, the

S_{11} simulation values will not match the experimental data, as is shown in Figure 9.

Fig. 7. Experimental and simulated data with/without C_{js} and C_{gb} for the magnitude and phase of S_{22} . Also, V_{gs} , V_{ds} , V_{bs} are equal to 0V.

Fig. 8. Experimental and simulated data of the proposed model and of the model in [2] for S_{22} . Also, V_{gs} , V_{ds} , V_{bs} are equal to 0V.

Fig. 9. Experimental and simulated data of the proposed model and of the model in [2] for S_{11} . Also, V_{gs} , V_{ds} , V_{bs} are equal to 0V.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

A simple methodology to extract the substrate parasitic network was herein presented. In turn, this method was used to characterize devices in which the source and substrate are disconnected. In this case, there is a separate substrate DC connection. Two-port S-parameters measurements were performed on this type of devices, demonstrating that the proposed model agrees very well with experimental data. A clear advantage of this method is that capacitances C_{gs} , C_{gd} , C_{js} and C_{jd} can be independently determined, allowing for a deeper knowledge of the parasitic components present in an RF-MOSFET. This proposal provides a simple characterization methodology based on two-port S-parameter measurements in a new RF-MOSFET structure with separate substrate DC connections. This allows the designer to simulate complex circuits in which the substrate and the bulk are biased at different potentials.

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